

ANALYSIS OF THE TOURISM DEVELOPMENT POTENTIAL OF THE BUKHARA REGION

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Abstract

This article highlights the notion of “tourist potential”, comparing its difference from the “tourist resource”. Methods for evaluating tourist potential are investigated and discussed. The tourism potential of the Bukhara region, as well as the actual state of the region's tourist market, are detailed. The article discusses the state's efforts to promote the tourism business following the coronavirus outbreak. The author suggests many strategies for Ministries, departments, and subordinate bodies to promote the region's tourist growth.

Keywords: Tourism Potential, Uzbekistan, Bukhara Region, Bukhara, Region, Tourism Resource, Integral Assessment, Tourism Industry

INTRODUCTION

The tourist potential of any territory (or object) is a collection of man-made and natural bodies and phenomena associated with the territory (or object), as well as opportunities, conditions, and means for the development of a tourist product and the implementation of relevant excursions, tours, and programs. In comparison to the idea of “tourist potential,” the concept of “tourist resource” operates as a larger, communal one. According to the above formulations, it is clear that the concept of “tourist resource” has a narrower focus and involves one specific resource that may distinguish this object, whereas “tourist potential” is a broader concept that implies a complex of all potential, cultural, historical, natural, and socioeconomic grounds for organizing tourism activities in the specified territory.

The tourist potential is also known as the ratio of the greatest possible to the actual number of tourists, which is governed by the availability of tourism resources. However, some experts believe that this is incorrect. Potential is the availability of reserves in a certain region, chances that may be utilized under particular conditions to accomplish the desired goal – the formation of tourism.

An integrative evaluation of any object's or zone's hospitality industry potential is conditional, because it necessarily involves qualitative indications and can only be read conditionally in contrast to another object's assessment of potential. This means that, in accordance with the specifics of the accepted scale, at least five or seven objects must be in the field of view (depending on the number of scale gradations) during evaluation (comparison), and it is always recommended to specifically identify within which area both comparison and evaluation of potentials are performed.

As a comparative evaluation, it makes sense to identify and analyze a region's tourist potential:

- a) Explicitly defining the geographical field of comparison;
- b) Calculating the final grade using qualitative scales in their scoring form;
- c) Include the required number of assessment items in the comparison assessment;
- d) Assessing the existing collection of prospective components.

Many writers conducted similar investigations, including D.G. Mamrayeva 2020, L.V. Tashenova 2020, Kirilchuk S.P. 2021, and Music A.S.2021.

Literature review. D.G. Mamrayeva and L.V. Tashenova created methodological methods for measuring the region's tourism and recreational potential (TRP). The authors have established an enhanced criterion basis that enables for a full multi-factorial assessment of the region's TRP, covering the 5 most major blocks of potential assessment with the following parameters:

1. "Natural resources and circumstances";
2. "Cultural and historical assets"
3. "Tourist infrastructure provision";
4. "Tourist information security";
5. "Limited factors".¹

In all, 97 most relevant and appealing criteria were discovered across all five blocks.

Because it incorporates analytical tools for analyzing the TRP of the region, this approach for assessing the TRP of the region allows for an objective assessment of the region's status and chances for development.

The technique for analyzing the resource potential of tourism created by Kirilchuk S.P. and Muzyka A.S. includes in detail a large number of aspects impacting the evaluation of the region's tourist potential, as well as expert opinion, and an in-depth study is done on the basis of this. Because some data in the tourist sector cannot be evaluated and accurate statistics obtained (for example, the actual number of pilgrims visiting a mosque), this technique is a subjective assessment of tourism's resource potential. However, it incorporates objective facts and criteria that are considered while computing the five-stage decomposition analysis method.²

This technique calls for the creation and testing of an effective methodological approach for estimating resource and tourist potential via the use of practical instruments.

When establishing the stage sequence, it was taken into account that a substantial portion of potential and current tourist destinations in the research region lack trustworthy data on tourism dynamics. As a result, the technique is based on the weighted sum model, a prominent multi-criteria decision tool that contains ranking and scaling methods to quantify numerous aspects, in order to produce an optimum conclusion in this respect.

The synthesis of the decomposition method, the weighted sum method, the method of expert survey by the ranking method, normalization of intra-attribute scaling, and clustering were chosen for simplicity and reliability, subject to the use of qualitative and quantitative data, and while limiting the presence of individual statistical gaps in this study. This methodological technique is implemented in five steps that are carried out sequentially:

This strategy incorporates physical, social, and appealing characteristics. Which, in turn, include second-level qualities. That is, a social attribute of the first level, for example, comprises of qualities of the second level, such as visitor attendance and current events. Physical characteristics of the first level include physical characteristics of the second level, such as transportation and pedestrian accessibility, social infrastructure, and so on. Attractive first-level traits contain the following second-level attributes: for example, recognition, etc.

Those. This approach examines all elements objectively before calculating and evaluating the tourist potential of the location under consideration. An efficient approach for estimating tourist potential in the face of erroneous and insufficient data.

The selection of an option for planning the growth of forms of tourism and the tourist market should be based on an examination of the region's resource base, the status of tourism firms, and the availability of demand for a tourist product.

Consider the growth and function of the tourist industry in the Bukhara region.

The Bukhara region, being one of Uzbekistan's most important and growing regions, provides several prospects for economic growth through tourism industry. And the region has a significant number of requirements and chances for this.

Table 1 will look at the Bukhara area's contribution to the growth of the region and the country as a whole:

Table 1: Key indicators of the tourism industry in Uzbekistan³

Indicators	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020 ⁴	2021 ⁵
The number of tourists who entered the country, thousand people	4 145,6	5182,5	8594,8	8437,8	2001,5	2194,8
Number of hotels and similar accommodation facilities	750	816	916	1051	1152	848
Number of places in hotels and similar accommodation facilities, in thousand	37,8	39,8	40,8	46,7	50,1	43,5
Number of visitors accommodated in hotels and similar accommodation facilities, in thousand	1531,1	1714,2	2 125,9	2 193,4	702,8	1057,7
Nights spent by visitors to hotels and similar accommodation facilities, thousand person-days	3887,8	4181,8	4 693,9	4 838,9	768,5	2584,0
Number of recreation organizations and tourist bases	251	298	376	531	425	328
Training of specialists by higher educational institutions in the field of tourism, students in total	1731	1932	1628	2799	-	-

Table 2: The main indicators of the tourism industry in the Bukhara region⁶

Indicator	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020 ⁷	2021 ⁸
Number of hotels and similar accommodation facilities	104	125	140	173	189	193
Number of places in hotels and similar accommodation facilities, in thousand	3,7	3,8	4,1	5,1	6,5	10,3
Number of visitors accommodated in hotels and similar accommodation facilities, in thousand	118,5	144,0	190,2	220,6	1,1	225,0
Nights spent by visitors to hotels and similar facilities, thousand person-days	233,9	279,1	384,0	409,0	82,0	467,0
Number of recreation organizations and tourist bases	1	5	34	49	-	7
Training of specialists by higher educational institutions in the field of tourism, students in total	-	-	103	118	-	-

According to the statistics in the preceding tables, the Bukhara region's contribution to Uzbekistan's tourist sector is relatively substantial, and it plays a leading position in the country in several ways. This shows that tourism in the region is quite important and has a significant impact on the region's economy. According to hotel and travel company practices, travelers who visit Uzbekistan spend the majority of their time in Bukhara, which serves as a transshipment hub between Tashkent and Khiva or Samarkand and Khiva. They remain in Bukhara for three nights and effectively spend three days since there are more cultural items to view here than, say, in Samarkand, where you can see all the sites in one day, or Tashkent, where there is a historically significant wealth of cultural things but not in big number. Taking advantage of this feature, it is vital to broaden the cultural and entertainment basis in the Bukhara region, as well as to build new facilities for leisure and visiting visitors. Despite the situation that has arisen all over the world, including in our republic, as a result of the COVID-19 coronavirus pandemic, 78 new large and small hotels have been built thanks to the business

conditions created by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the government in the Bukhara region (724 rooms fund, 1919 placements). In all, the number of tourist lodgings in the region reached 415 units by the end of 2021. (4465 rooms, 10328 accommodations). Objects are classified based on the number of placements as follows (Table 3):

Table 3: Accommodation facilities by category in Bukhara region for 2021

Accommodation facilities	Number of accommodation facilities	Number of rooms	Number of placements
Hotels	163	3320	6974
Family guest houses	197	682	1837
Hostels	52	429	1456
Motels	1	29	51
Apartments	2	5	10
Total:	415	4465	10328

In terms of the number of hotels, the Bukhara area ranks second in the country behind Tashkent, indicating favorable economic indications in the region's tourist business. The number of persons employed in the Bukhara region's tourist and service sectors has also increased, as shown below:

Table 4: Data on employed in tourism in Bukhara region ⁹

Name of activity	Total quantity	Newly created in 2021
Tour operators	121	2
Tour guides	252	20
Restaurants for tourists	90	3
Tourist buses and minibuses	281	-
Tourist signs	128	5
Tourist information centers	26	5

These figures suggest that, despite global uncertainty, work on the development and expansion of the tourism business in the Bukhara region is going in a healthy direction. In 2021, 2,265,465 visitors visited Bukhara as a result of initiatives implemented in the republic to develop and encourage tourism and business. There are 2,216,465 local visitors and 48,926 international tourists among them. These results are greater than the given period in 2020 and demonstrate an increase: 9.3 times for local tourists and 3.6 times for overseas tourists. In the form of advantages and benefits, the municipal budget granted 22.2 billion soums to tourism-related businesses. Subsidies of 2.04 billion soums were granted for the development of the Turon Plaza hotel in particular. In accordance with the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan's Decree No. UP-6002 "On Urgent Measures to Support the Tourism Sector to Reduce the Negative Impact of the Coronavirus Pandemic," dated May 28, 2020, commercial banks extended loans from 6 months to 2 years to 30 business entities in the region (25 of them from the city of Bukhara). The extension affected 18.6 billion soums out of 79.4 billion soums, or over a quarter of the entire amount of business loans given.¹⁰ In the Bukhara area, 78 enterprises will receive tax breaks worth 1.2 billion soums in 2021, while 27 entrepreneurs (including three tour operators worth 41 million soums and 24 hotels for 1 billion 604 million soums) would receive loans worth 1.6 billion soums. A total of 40 million dollars in grant funding were

granted for the introduction and development of new sectors of tourism for two travel firms and six tour guides. More than 20 cultural events and festivals have been planned in order to attract a large number of foreign and domestic tourists to Bukhara in 2021. There are many such “Nasridin Afandi”, “Oriental delicacies”, “Silk and spices”, “Melon Festival”, “Artisans of Bukhara”, “Day of the City of Bukhara”, International conference “Abu Ali ibn Sino” in the hamlet of Afsona, fair and competition “Experienced cook”, International forum “Youth tourism”. At addition, the 500th anniversary of the Mir Arab madrassa was celebrated, a calligraphy competition was conducted in the Bahouddin Naqshband complex, and following the competition, a conference dedicated to Islamic calligraphy was held, and the Muezzin Competition was held.¹¹ According to forecasts from the “Bukhara Regional Department of Tourism and Sports,” tourism services would provide 478.9 billion soums to the regional budget in 2021. (of which 79.9 billion soums came from foreign tourists). This amount is 9.7 times that of 2020.

The Cultural Heritage Agency under the Ministry of Tourism and Cultural Heritage of the Republic of Uzbekistan needs:

- Preserve cultural heritage artifacts in their original form, as they have survived to this day. With the exception of approved preservation techniques, in order to maintain them in their original form and avoid further dilapidation and destruction. Cultural heritage artifacts have the connotation of not only being conductors of the transfer of our predecessors' cultural legacy, but also a role in the development of public education, national culture and art, science and education. Today, this issue is significant for all cultural property artifacts, since such “illiterate” restoration work is being carried out throughout the country, particularly in the Bukhara region. Objects are brought to an ideal “luminous” and new condition, where its original charm, a distinguishing trait, is gone, and the structures become identical to one another. Monuments, mosques, madrasahs, and minarets begin to resemble one another in every area of Uzbekistan. Where visitors grumble about seeing the same “three Ms”¹² (mosque, minaret, and madrasah) on the tourist route across Uzbekistan. However, this is due to the fact that the restoration work is done illiterately, and the structures are merely rebuilt. The solution to this problem can be:
 1. Involve national and international specialists who are familiar with the characteristics of historical object construction, are familiar with natural occurrences in the region, and have researched building materials and building construction processes in the Bukhara region to establish a restoration work plan;
 2. To attract masters who study and practice Bukhara usto traditional culture and have the certification of a master.;
 3. Total command and tight accountability for all funds granted and spent on repair efforts;
 4. Guaranteeing the protection of cultural heritage places for at least 15 years, with personal accountability for each one.

- Control the development of structures and the execution of construction activities near historical and cultural landmarks to prevent additional deterioration. Because vibrations, eroding, and strong activities near historical monuments are risky, these structures may not be able to endure such a load.
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The Ministry of Tourism and Cultural Heritage of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Ministry for the Development of Information Technologies and Communications of the Republic of Uzbekistan:

- Create an easily accessible and popular program to ensure the seamless circulation of tourists across the nation. Those will develop an application that will allow tourists to travel the nation, particularly the Bukhara region, on their own. It will be sufficient to download the application, which will result in the following positions:
 1. A visitor will be able to obtain information on the ideal time to visit Uzbekistan, namely the Bukhara region;
 2. Promotions and seasonal offers from travel firms, hotels, and so on;
 3. Affordably priced air tickets from your country to Uzbekistan, specifically to the international airport of the city of Bukhara, as well as tickets for trains and planes inside the country;
 4. Interesting routes of travel throughout the city, created for 1 week, 3 days, and 2 days off.
 5. Tourists will be able to pay at historical and cultural institutions, eating centers, hotels, stores, and other tourist-oriented establishments.
- Create a single travel card for the payment of goods and services by a foreign person while on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
- Create interactive information points for providing free mobility information in Bukhara and the surrounding area. These information stations should be located in tourist areas, beginning with the international airport of Bukhara, the railway station in Kagan, the bus station in the city of Bukhara, cultural and historical landmarks, tourist food outlets, handicraft centers, and near hotels. The following services must be given in these information centers in the world's common languages:
 1. How to travel to a specific item from a given position (what is the distance, how long can you get on foot and by transportation, quick or short route, and so on);
 2. The burden of historical and cultural places, in order to organize and visit routes more efficiently;

3. Profitable offers, promotions, and so on at hotels, cafés, restaurants, and recreational facilities;
 4. In an emergency, call for assistance;
 5. Charging stations for mobile gadgets.
- Create a real-time information portal about tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan, complete with specific information about:
 1. relics of historical and cultural significance;
 2. Leisure and cultural and educational destinations;
 3. A year-ahead calendar of events, fairs, festivals, concerts, and so on, so that anyone planning a trip to Uzbekistan may plan ahead of time;
 4. The country's weather at various periods of the year;
 5. Exchange rates and payment methods for products and services in the nation;
 6. Conduct and stay rules in the country;
 7. Hotels, guest homes, and other forms of lodging;
 8. Traditions, traditions, and culture of Uzbekistan's regions;
 9. Each region's national cuisine;
 10. Visa assistance;
 11. Purchase of airline and train tickets;
 12. Tour self-organization assistance;
 13. Contacts for dealing with emergencies and existing concerns;
 14. A separate column for after-visit feedback and ideas.

Civil Aviation Agency under the Ministry of Transport of the Republic of Uzbekistan:

- Allow a big number of air firms access to the country's international airports in order to increase the flow of foreign individuals into the country.;
- Collaboration with regional carriers Flights inside the country are convenient, frequent, and regular, allowing for easy travel from area to region. Flights must be planned in accordance with demand data and flow to certain regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan, particularly historically significant cities with a consistent demand for visitors, independent of tourist seasons;
- Due to the fame of the historic city of Bukhara across the world, actively employ the city of Bukhara's international airport to boost its competitiveness, demand, and arrivals in the country.

Local airlines “Uzbekistan Airways” and “Qanot Sharq Airlines” are urged to take action on the following concerns, which are critical to the entry of international tourists on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan:

- Rethink flight price in favor of decreasing it, which will significantly enhance the flow of tourists into the nation. Prices for goods and services in Uzbekistan are very affordable for foreign citizens of any country in the world, and this is the most important factor when choosing our country as a destination, but ticket prices to Uzbekistan are many times more expensive than if travelers choose Turkey, Egypt, or any other European country for their route. And in the case of rejection to visit our nation, this aspect is frequently crucial;
- Add more convenient flights for local flights from one city to another, considering demand statistics for these locations and the flow of movement of local and international populations into consideration. Also, while building new domestic routes, it is important to set competitive pricing to ensure consistent demand for air tickets in these areas.
- Create a discount scheme for different types of passengers or group trips, and set fair low-season flight ticket costs.;
- Develop a city tour for transit passengers for a short length of time, up to several hours, in collaboration with the Ministry of Tourism and Cultural Heritage of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Main Department of Tourism and Sports of the Bukhara area. Thus, popularizing Bukhara among a big number of foreign citizens will be effective. Furthermore, such excursions promote the growth of commerce in local goods and services.

Notes

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